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dolescence and cardiosomatics: diagnostic methods and possible risks

Adolescencia y cardiosomática: métodos de diagnóstico y posibles riesgos

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Abstract

Adolescence is a period of active physical and psycho-emotional development accompanied by significant changes in the cardiovascular system. Cardiosomatics, which investigates the influence of psychoemotional factors on cardiac health, plays an important role in the study of cardiovascular problems in adolescents. The main focus is on how stress, anxiety, emotional overload and developmental characteristics during this period can affect the heart and vascular health.

Physiological changes such as hormonal changes, increased metabolism and heart muscle growth are accompanied by increased sensitivity of the nervous system. This leads to the risk of developing functional disorders such as autonomic dysfunction syndrome (ADS), psychogenic cardialgia - pain in the heart area caused by emotional factors, arrhythmias.

The following diagnostic methods are used for early de-

tection of cardiosomatic disorders: clinical examination, instrumental methods, psychological testing, and laboratory tests.

Untimely detection and treatment of cardiosomatic disorders can lead to serious consequences, such as the formation of persistent functional disorders such as chronic tachycardia or arterial hypertension, psychosomatic disorders that develop into neuroses or depressive states, reduced quality of life, deterioration of physical endurance and cognitive activity.

Thus, diagnosis of cardiosomatic disorders in adolescents requires a comprehensive approach combining medical and psychological methods, which will minimise risks and improve quality of life in adolescence and in the future.

Keywords: adolescence, cardiosomatics, cardiovascular system, stress, psychosomatics, diagnosis, autonomic dysfunction, tachycardia, arrhythmia.

La adolescencia es un período de desarrollo físico y psicoemocional activo acompañado de cambios significativos en el sistema cardiovascular. La cardiosomática, que investiga la influencia de los factores psicoemocionales en la salud cardíaca, desempeña un papel importante en el estudio de los problemas cardiovasculares en los adolescentes. La atención se centra principalmente en cómo el estrés, la ansiedad, la sobrecarga emocional y las características del desarrollo durante este período pueden afectar la salud cardíaca y vascular.

Los cambios fisiológicos como los cambios hormonales, el aumento del metabolismo y el crecimiento del músculo cardíaco van acompañados de una mayor sensibilidad del sistema nervioso. Esto conduce al riesgo de desarrollar trastornos funcionales como el síndrome de disfunción autonómica (SDA), cardialgia psicógena: dolor en el área del corazón causado por factores emocionales y arritmias.

Para la detección temprana de trastornos cardiológicos se utilizan los siguientes métodos de diagnóstico: examen clínico, métodos instrumentales, pruebas psicológicas y pruebas de laboratorio.

La detección y el tratamiento inoportunos de los trastornos cardiosomáticos pueden tener consecuencias graves, como la formación de trastornos funcionales persistentes como taquicardia crónica o hipertensión arterial, trastornos psicósomáticos que se convierten en neurosis o estados depresivos, reducción de la calidad de vida, deterioro de la resistencia física y cognitiva. actividad.

Así, el diagnóstico de los trastornos cardiosomáticos en adolescentes requiere un abordaje integral que combine métodos médicos y psicológicos, que minimicen los riesgos y mejoren la calidad de vida en la adolescencia y en el futuro.

Palabras clave: adolescencia, cardiosomática, sistema cardiovascular, estrés, psicósomática, diagnóstico, disfunción autonómica, taquicardia, arritmia.

Adolescence is a key stage of human development characterised by significant physical, emotional and social changes¹. During this period, not only the personality of the adolescent is formed, but also the main physiological systems, including the cardiovascular system, are actively rearranged. Hormonal surges, increased sensitivity to stress factors, as well as features of adaptation to the social environment can provoke the development of cardiosomatic disorders.

Cardiosomatics, which studies the relationship between psycho-emotional state and cardiac function, is becoming an important field in adolescent medicine. Modern research confirms that functional disorders of the cardiovascular system, such as arrhythmias, autonomic dysfunctions and psychogenic cardialgia, often have a psychosomatic nature. Lack of timely diagnosis and treatment of such conditions can lead to a deterioration in the quality of life, and in some cases - to serious diseases in adulthood.

The introduction of modern diagnostic and prevention methods, including instrumental and psychological approaches, makes it possible to minimise risks and maintain adolescent health during this critical period of life.

Materials and Methods. In the process of writing the article, we conducted a study of existing literature, scientific articles and data on cardiosomatics and adolescent health, highlighting the main factors influencing the development of cardiosomatic disorders (biological, psychological, social), as well as analysing modern methods of diagnosing cardiovascular disorders in adolescence.

A unified concept describing the interaction of cardiological and psychoemotional factors was formed, also the features of cardiosomatics in adolescence were compared with other age groups, as well as the identification of common patterns in the development of cardiovascular disorders in adolescence and the generalisation of research results for the formation of recommendations on diagnosis and prevention.

Adolescence is an important stage of human development, covering the period from 12 to 18 years of age, when there is an intensive formation of physical, psycho-emotional and social potential of an individual. This age is characterised by active growth of the organism, hormonal restructuring, formation of personal qualities and assimilation of social roles. At the same time, the cardiovascular system of adolescents undergoes significant changes associated with adaptation to the increased load on the body and acceleration of metabolic processes.

The peculiarities of this period often provoke the appearance of functional disorders, which, although not associated with organic pathology, can significantly affect the quality of life. This is explained by the high sensitivity of the adolescent organism to external and internal influences. Against the background of hormonal changes and increased metabolic activity, adolescents become more vulnerable to the influence of such factors as stress, emotional tension, psychological overload, unstable interpersonal relationships, and learning loads².

Cardiosomatics, as an interdisciplinary branch of medicine, deals with the study of how psychoemotional states and psychological characteristics of a person can be reflected in the cardiovascular system. In adolescents, this relationship is particularly pronounced in the form of functional disorders such as autonomic dysfunction, psychogenic cardialgia, arterial hypertension, tachycardia and arrhythmias. These conditions, although not organically based, can cause serious discomfort and anxiety for both adolescents and their parents.

Stress and anxiety play a key role in the emergence of cardiosomatic problems in adolescence. In conditions of emotional instability associated with the transition age, adolescents may experience increased irritability, anxiety and difficulties in social adaptation. These psychoemotional states affect vascular tone, heart rate and blood pressure, which in turn leads to subjective feelings of pain, heart palpitations and other complaints³.

An equally important factor is the lifestyle of adolescents. Reduced physical activity, prolonged stay in stressful situations (e.g., during school), as well as improper nutrition and insufficient sleep aggravate the risks of cardiosomatic disorders. All this emphasises the need for a comprehensive approach to the diagnosis and prevention of such conditions, including not only medical, but also psychological and social aspects.

Thus, the study of the relationship between psychoemotional state and cardiovascular system in adolescence is important for the preservation of adolescent health.

This requires the introduction of modern diagnostic techniques, including cardiological examination tools, psychological tests and analysis of lifestyle factors. Taking preventive measures and early correction of functional disorders will help to avoid complications, ensure harmonious development and lay the foundation for health in adulthood.

Physiological changes such as hormonal restructuring, increased metabolism and heart muscle growth are accompanied by increased sensitivity of the nervous system, leading to the risk of developing functional disorders.

Autonomic dysfunction (autonomic vascular dystonia, ADS) is a complex of disorders associated with uncoordinated operation of the autonomic nervous system, which is responsible for the regulation of vital body functions: cardiac activity, respiration, blood circulation, digestion and thermoregulation. In adolescents, this syndrome manifests itself especially often due to active hormonal restructuring, rapid physical growth and instability of psychoemotional state⁴.

During puberty there is a significant increase in the activity of the endocrine system (pituitary, adrenal and sex glands), which affects the autonomic nervous system. This leads to its hyperreactivity or imbalance. Adolescents often have stressful situations related to learning, social relationships, self-esteem, which contributes to overstrain the nervous system. If parents or close relatives in the family have functional disorders of the cardiovascular system, it increases the likelihood of their manifestation in adolescents.

Intense sports activities, lack of sleep, prolonged time spent in front of gadget screens can deplete the body's reserve resources. Unbalanced nutrition, lack of vitamins and microelements (especially magnesium and potassium), as well as irregular sleep have a negative impact on the autonomic system.

Autonomic dysfunction manifests itself polymorphously, and symptoms can range from mild discomfort to severe conditions. Thus, autonomic dysfunction in adolescents is a reversible condition that, if diagnosed in time and properly corrected, can avoid complications and improve the quality of life⁵.

Psychogenic cardialgia is pain in the heart region, arising against the background of emotional and psychological factors. In adolescence, such disorders are especially common due to unstable psychoemotional state associated with hormonal restructuring, increased sensitivity to stress and peculiarities of social adaptation.

Psychogenic cardialgia is pain in the heart region, which arises under the influence of emotional and psychological factors. In adolescents, such conditions are observed especially often due to unstable psycho-emotional background associated with hormonal restructuring, increased sensitivity to stress and difficulties in social ad-

aptation. These disorders are not organic, but functional in nature, but can cause significant discomfort.

The causes of psychogenic cardialgia in adolescents are related to a number of factors. An important role is played by stressful situations and anxiety, which adolescents experience because of examinations, conflicts with others, high academic load or difficulties in relations with peers. Psychoemotional tension arising against the background of these factors increases the sensitivity of the nervous system, provoking the subjective sensation of pain⁶. An important factor is heredity: the tendency to psychosomatic reactions can be transmitted from parents. The environment of the adolescent also has a significant impact. Peer pressure, problems in the family, school bullying or dissatisfaction with one's appearance can lead to long-term emotional tension.

Heart pain in psychogenic cardialgia is usually localised on the left side of the chest and is described by adolescents as «stabbing», «pressing» or «burning». They most often occur in moments of psycho-emotional tension and are not associated with physical exertion, which distinguishes them from pain in organic heart disease. Often the pains are accompanied by subjective sensations, such as heaviness in the chest, a feeling of heart freezing or pulsation. In addition, there may be associated symptoms of autonomic dysfunction: sweating, palpitations, dyspnoea, dizziness⁷.

Diagnosis of psychogenic cardialgia requires the exclusion of organic heart pathology, which is achieved through a comprehensive examination, including medical examination, electrocardiography, echocardiography and, if necessary, Holter monitoring. Daily monitoring of the heart helps to identify the functional nature of violations. In addition, the adolescent may be referred for psychological testing to assess the level of anxiety and emotional state.

Treatment of psychogenic cardialgia requires a comprehensive approach. An important stage is work with a psychologist or psychotherapist who helps the adolescent learn to cope with stress and anxiety. Effective methods of cognitive-behavioural therapy, aimed at eliminating irrational fears and the formation of positive thinking. Of great importance is the correction of lifestyle, including normalisation of sleep patterns, regular physical activity and proper nutrition. Physiotherapy can also be useful: massage, water procedures and relaxation techniques help to relieve tension. In some cases, mild sedatives, such as those based on herbal components, may be prescribed⁸.

Prevention of psychogenic cardialgia includes creation of a favourable psychological environment in the family, emotional support of the adolescent, formation of healthy habits and teaching stress management skills. With timely detection and proper therapy, psychogenic cardialgia does not pose a threat to the health and life

of the adolescent, but ignoring the problem can lead to a deterioration in the quality of life and emotional state.

Arrhythmias are heart rhythm disturbances that can occur in healthy adolescents as well as in those suffering from various functional disorders. In adolescence, these disorders may be functional rather than organic in nature. The causes of arrhythmias in adolescents are both physiological features and psychoemotional factors such as stress, anxiety, emotional overload and active changes in the body associated with the transition age. During this period there is an intense hormonal restructuring, which can affect the work of the heart, disturbing the balance of the autonomic nervous system, which regulates the heart rhythm. In addition, adolescents often experience strong emotions, which can be a trigger for arrhythmias.

Arrhythmias in adolescents can manifest themselves as rapid heartbeat (tachycardia), slow heart rate (bradycardia), and irregular heart rhythm (extrasystole), in which the heart feels like it is racing. These disorders may be accompanied by a feeling of «jumping» or «pounding» in the chest area, as well as severe fatigue, dizziness, shortness of breath and general weakness. In some cases, adolescents may not notice rhythm disturbances if they are mild, but in more severe forms of arrhythmias, there is a decrease in performance and discomfort in everyday life⁹.

A number of tests are performed to diagnose arrhythmias in adolescence. The main method is electrocardiography (ECG), which can detect any changes in heart rhythm. If necessary, daily Holter monitoring may be prescribed, which helps to track arrhythmias throughout the day, taking into account various physical and emotional stresses. An echocardiographic study may also be performed to rule out organic heart disease.

Treatment of arrhythmias in adolescents depends largely on their nature. If the arrhythmia is functional, then the main attention is paid to the correction of the psychoemotional state, relieving stress and anxiety. In this case, psychotherapy, relaxation practices, as well as drugs to normalise the nervous system, such as plant-based sedatives, can be prescribed. It is also important to pay attention to the lifestyle of the teenager: a regular sleep schedule, physical activity, proper nutrition and lack of overload will contribute to the normalisation of the heart rhythm. If the arrhythmia is accompanied by more serious symptoms or health risks, medications may be used to normalise the heart rhythm, but such medications should only be prescribed by a doctor.

Thus, arrhythmias in adolescents may be associated with physiological changes in the body, stress and emotional experiences characteristic of adolescence. With timely medical attention and a proper approach to treatment, functional arrhythmias do not pose a threat to health, and most of them can be effectively corrected using conservative methods¹⁰.

Hyperkinetic heart syndrome is a condition in which there is an excessive increase in cardiac output, accompanied by a rapid heartbeat and a pulsation sensation in the head and neck area. This condition can be particularly pronounced in adolescents during puberty, when there are intense changes in the body, including hormonal changes, heart muscle growth and metabolic acceleration. As a result, the adolescent heart begins to work with increased workload, which may manifest itself as hyperkinetic reactions.

Hyperkinetic heart syndrome can develop against a background of stress, physical overload or emotional distress, which is especially relevant for adolescents experiencing emotional and social changes during this period¹¹. Physical activity or even emotional stress, such as exams or conflicts at school, can be triggers for increased heart activity, causing the adolescent to feel tachycardia (rapid heartbeat), throbbing in the head or neck area, and a feeling of pressure in the chest. It is important to note that the heart condition remains within normal limits and there are no signs of organic disease or abnormalities.

Symptoms of hyperkinetic heart syndrome may include not only palpitations, but also dizziness, weakness, increased fatigue, and feelings of anxiety and restlessness. Adolescents may complain of a feeling of «palpitations» in the heart, and this is often accompanied by an emotional response, such as increased panic or anxiety attacks. Such conditions may occur as a response to stressful or physical exertion and usually disappear after normalisation of the psycho-emotional background and rest. However, in some cases, symptoms may persist for a long time and cause significant discomfort.

For diagnosis of hyperkinetic heart syndrome, it is important to perform a comprehensive examination including electrocardiography (ECG) to exclude organic causes of palpitations and exercise tests to assess cardiac performance under stress. Holter monitoring can accurately identify periods of palpitations and determine their relationship to emotional or physical stress¹².

Treatment of hyperkinetic heart syndrome, as a rule, does not require cardinal drug interventions. In most cases, lifestyle correction is sufficient. This includes normalisation of the daily regime with sufficient sleep, regular physical activity, avoidance of stressful situations, as well as a balanced diet. An important element of treatment is work with the psycho-emotional state of the adolescent: psychotherapy, relaxation practices and stress reduction methods such as breathing exercises and meditation can significantly help in reducing symptoms. In cases of severe disturbances, herbal sedatives or heart medications may be prescribed, but these measures are only used in severe cases.

Thus, hyperkinetic heart syndrome in adolescents is most often a functional condition caused by stress or overload, and usually does not require serious medi-

cal intervention. Timely diagnosis and proper treatment aimed at eliminating stress factors and normalising the lifestyle can quickly improve the adolescent's condition and prevent possible complications.

Tachycardia and bradycardia are among the most common heart rhythm disorders in adolescents. These disorders can be caused both by physiological changes occurring in the body during puberty and by psycho-emotional factors such as stress, anxiety, depression and emotional overload¹³.

Tachycardia is a rapid heartbeat in which the heart rate exceeds 100 beats per minute. In adolescents, tachycardia can develop due to various causes, both physiological and pathophysiological. For example, physical activity, emotional distress or stressful situations can be provocateurs of tachycardia, especially in adolescents who are undergoing hormonal changes and facing increased emotional stress. In such cases, tachycardia is of a functional nature and usually disappears after elimination of stress factors or normalisation of physical condition.

Symptoms of tachycardia may include palpitations, dizziness, weakness, shortness of breath, and feelings of anxiety and restlessness. In some cases, tachycardia can be accompanied by chest pain and even loss of consciousness if the heart rate becomes extremely high. It is important to note that although tachycardia can be caused by emotional or physical overload, in some cases it can be a symptom of underlying heart disease such as myocarditis or cardiomyopathy, which requires more careful diagnosis.

Bradycardia, on the other hand, is a condition in which the heart rate falls below 60 beats per minute. Bradycardia in adolescents is generally less common than tachycardia and in most cases is a physiological condition, especially in physically active adolescents, such as athletes. In these cases, a slow heartbeat is associated with a well-trained cardiovascular system and does not pose a health risk. However, in some situations, bradycardia may be associated with various diseases or conduction disorders of the heart, such as sinus node weakness syndrome, which requires medical intervention.

Symptoms of bradycardia may include fatigue, dizziness, fainting, and feelings of weakness and shortness of breath. If bradycardia leads to impaired blood supply to organs and tissues, more serious consequences may occur, such as exacerbation of chronic diseases, decreased performance and even loss of consciousness¹⁴.

To diagnose tachycardia and bradycardia in adolescents, a standardised examination is performed, including electrocardiography (ECG), which records the rate and regularity of heartbeats. If necessary, Holter monitoring may be prescribed to assess the heart's performance throughout the day and identify episodes of rhythm disturbance. Echocardiography may also be required to rule out organic heart disease.

Treatment of tachycardia and bradycardia in adolescents depends on the cause of rhythm disturbances. In most cases, if these conditions are functional in nature, it is sufficient to correct lifestyle, normalise psycho-emotional state and eliminate stress factors. Adolescents are recommended to follow a regular daily regime, engage in physical activity, avoid overload and stress. If tachycardia or bradycardia is caused by pathological processes, it may require drug therapy aimed at restoring normal heart rhythm or treating the underlying disease.

Thus, tachycardia and bradycardia in adolescence are most often functional conditions associated with the peculiarities of the organism and psycho-emotional overload. It is important to seek medical help in time to diagnose and determine the possible causes of rhythm disturbances, as well as to prescribe appropriate treatment, which in most cases is conservative and aimed at restoring normal heart function.

Autonomic dysfunction syndrome, or autonomic dystonia (ADS), is a common disorder that occurs in adolescents and often affects the cardiovascular system. This condition is accompanied by abnormalities in the autonomic nervous system, which regulates many bodily functions, including heart rate, blood pressure, and vascular tone. In adolescence, ADS often develops against the background of intensive changes in the body, such as hormonal restructuring, as well as under the influence of stress factors, emotional overload and improper lifestyle¹⁵.

Autonomic dysfunction syndrome can present with a variety of symptoms, including rapid heartbeat (tachycardia), blood pressure fluctuations, dizziness, headaches, general weakness and fatigue. Teenagers with ADS often complain of unstable blood pressure, which can suddenly rise or fall, causing feelings of insecurity and anxiety. There may also be a feeling of shortness of breath, heart palpitations and a feeling of pressure in the chest. These symptoms may be exacerbated by stressful situations, physical exertion or emotional distress.

ADS in adolescents often develops against the background of psychoemotional stress caused by such factors as school exams, problems in the family or relations with peers, as well as worries about their appearance or social adaptation. Disorders of the autonomic nervous system may be associated with increased excitability or, conversely, with chronic fatigue and apathy. Psychological stress can exacerbate the symptoms of ADS, creating a vicious circle in which impaired autonomic regulation leads to a deterioration of general well-being, and the deterioration of well-being increases stress.

Diagnosis of autonomic dysfunction syndrome is based on the exclusion of other heart and vascular diseases. It is important to perform a complete examination of the patient, as well as to use research methods such as electrocardiography (ECG) to assess heart function and Holter monitoring to study changes in heart rhythm dur-

ing the day. Blood tests may also be ordered to assess the general condition of the body and rule out inflammatory conditions. In some cases, counselling by a psychotherapist or psychologist may be required to assess the adolescent's emotional state¹⁶.

Treatment of autonomic dysfunction syndrome in adolescents should be comprehensive and include both medical and psychological methods of action. First of all, it is important to eliminate the causes of stress and emotional overload, which may require working with a psychologist or psychotherapist. Techniques such as cognitive behavioural therapy aim to reduce anxiety and increase stress tolerance. Relaxation techniques such as breathing exercises, meditation and yoga are also effective.

Medication treatment of adolescent ADS is used when the symptoms of the disease are pronounced and lead to a significant deterioration in the quality of life. Usually it is the inclusion in the therapy of light sedatives, as well as drugs that can normalise the work of the autonomic nervous system. It is also important to pay attention to improving the general condition of the adolescent through lifestyle adjustments: balanced diet, sleep and rest regime, physical activity. Regular walks in the fresh air and moderate physical activity will help to improve the cardiovascular system and reduce stress levels.

Thus, autonomic dysfunction syndrome in adolescence is most often a consequence of stress and disorders of the psycho-emotional background. It is important to recognise the symptoms of this condition in time to avoid the development of chronic diseases. Timely diagnosis and treatment, including psychotherapeutic methods and lifestyle correction, can effectively cope with the manifestations of ADS and improve the quality of life of adolescents.

For early detection of cardiosomatic disorders in adolescents, several diagnostic methods are used to detect both functional disorders and exclude organic diseases of the cardiovascular system. The main diagnostic methods are presented in Table 1.

Electrocardiography (ECG) is a technique that measures the electrical activity of the heart. Using special electrodes placed on the patient's skin, the electrical potential that the heart generates during contractions is recorded. The ECG allows a detailed study of the rhythm of the heart, as well as the detection of various disorders such as tachycardia (rapid heartbeat), bradycardia (slow heartbeat), extrasystole (irregular heartbeats), as well as more complex disorders such as arrhythmias.

ECG is one of the most accessible and fastest diagnostic methods. However, its effectiveness is limited because it cannot always detect functional disorders that occur, for example, during stress or exercise¹⁷.

Holter monitoring is a method of long-term observation of electrocardiogram, which allows you to track the work of the heart for 24-48 hours. The patient wears a special portable device that continuously records the ECG. This method provides information about the condition of the heart under everyday conditions, including physical activity, stressful moments, and sleep. Holter monitoring is particularly useful for diagnosing tachycardias, extrasystoles and other disorders that may not always occur, but only at certain times (e.g. during stress or physical activity).

Echocardiography (cardiac ultrasound) is an ultrasound examination that allows you to visualise the structure of the heart, its valves, chambers, and to assess the function of the cardiovascular system. Echocardiography can detect anatomical changes such as heart defects, enlargement or thickening of the heart walls, and help detect inflammatory or degenerative heart disease.

Exercise tests, particularly the stress ECG (also known as a stress test), involve the patient performing physical exercise (e.g. on an exercise bike or treadmill) while an ECG is performed. This assesses how the heart works under stress and can detect hidden arrhythmias or other disorders that may not be apparent at rest.

Psychological testing includes various questionnaires and techniques aimed at identifying the level of stress, anxiety, depression and other emotional disorders. It is important because the psycho-emotional state can have a significant impact on the cardiovascular system, causing or aggravating cardiosomatic disorders. Psychologi-

cal testing helps to identify the emotional state of an adolescent and use the obtained data for further work with him/her, as well as for correction of the psychoemotional background, which is important for the elimination of cardiosomatic disorders¹⁸.

General blood tests and biochemical blood tests play an important role in assessing the overall health of an adolescent. These tests can rule out inflammatory or infectious diseases that may affect heart function, as well as detect changes in electrolyte or hormone levels that may be causing cardiosomatic disorders.

Cardiorespiratory testing is a method that assesses the interaction between the cardiovascular and respiratory systems. The test assesses both cardiac and respiratory parameters to help identify underlying disorders, such as autonomic nervous system dysfunction, which may be associated with cardiosomatic disorders. Cardiorespiratory testing is useful in diagnosing abnormalities that may be associated with cardiosomatic disorders and helps in the correction of respiratory and cardiac functions.

Thus, each of these diagnostic methods plays an important role in a comprehensive approach to identifying cardiosomatic disorders in adolescents, allowing not only to detect hidden problems, but also to develop effective treatment to eliminate the causes of disorders.

When diagnosing and treating cardiosomatic disorders in adolescents, it is necessary to take into account the possible risks that may be associated with both the peculiarities of the age period and the use of specific methods of diagnosis and treatment.

The risks associated with the diagnosis and treatment of cardiosomatic disorders in adolescents can be divided into several key categories. Physiological risks include the possibility of cardiovascular deterioration during certain diagnostic procedures, such as exercise tests or Holter monitoring, where stressful conditions can provoke arrhythmias, hypotension or hypertension. Psychoemotional risks are associated with increased anxiety in adolescents due to medical manipulation or awareness of a possible diagnosis, which is particularly relevant in settings where the adolescent is prone to stress or fear of medical procedures. Diagnostic errors represent another important concern, as limitations of methods or misinterpretation of results can lead to false positive or false negative findings, making timely and accurate treatment difficult.

Side effects of treatment are also a significant risk, especially with medications. For example, sedatives used to stabilise emotional states can cause drowsiness or reduced concentration, which can negatively affect an adolescent's academic and social functioning. Social risks can manifest themselves in the form of restricted physical activity, which can impair the adolescent's social adaptation, and excessive fixation on health can lead to isolation. Lifestyle disturbances, such as ignoring

recommendations for physical activity, diet or sleep patterns, can also exacerbate the condition or reduce the effectiveness of treatment. For example, fear of symptoms may lead to reduced motor activity, and disregarding dietary recommendations may worsen the overall condition¹⁹.

Of particular importance is the risk of a lack of a comprehensive approach, which may manifest itself by ignoring psycho-emotional factors or not working sufficiently with

the adolescent's family. Psycho-emotional aspects such as stress or anxiety often have a significant impact on the cardiovascular system, and ignoring them makes successful treatment more difficult. Lack of interaction with parents to create a supportive and comfortable environment can also reduce the effectiveness of treatment interventions and affect the overall emotional well-being of the adolescent²⁰. Taking all these aspects into account, it is important to develop an individualised approach to diagnosis and treatment that minimises these risks.

Table 1. Basic diagnostic methods

Diagnostic method	Description	Purpose/intent
Electrocardiography (ECG)	Measurement of the electrical activity of the heart to detect rhythm disturbances such as tachycardia, bradycardia, extrasystole.	Assessment of heart rhythm, detection of abnormalities in the electrical activity of the heart.
Holter monitoring	Prolonged ECG monitoring for 24-48 hours to monitor for latent rhythm disturbances occurring under conditions of stress or exercise.	Identification of hidden heart rhythm disorders, analysing their relationship to physical and emotional stress.
Echocardiography (cardiac ultrasound)	Ultrasound to evaluate the structure and function of the heart, detecting organic diseases such as heart defects, inflammation or size changes.	Exclusion of organic heart disease, evaluation of the structure and function of the heart chambers.
Physical activity tests	ECG under load for assessment of cardiac response to physical load, detection of hidden rhythm disturbances during exercise.	Assessment of cardiac function during exercise, detection of hidden rhythm disturbances associated with physical activity.
Psychological testing	Questionnaires and tests to assess levels of stress, anxiety, depression and other emotional disorders affecting heart health.	Assessment of the psycho-emotional state of the adolescent, identification of stress, anxiety and depression factors that may affect the cardiovascular system.
General blood count and biochemistry	Blood laboratory tests to assess the general condition of the body and to detect inflammation or infection.	Avoidance of inflammation and infectious diseases that can affect the cardiovascular system.
Cardiorespiratory testing	Assessment of the interaction of cardiovascular and respiratory systems, detection of disorders in their functioning.	Identification of cardiac and respiratory disorders that may be associated with cardiosomatic disorders and autonomic dysregulation.

Cardiosomatic disorders in adolescents represent an urgent medical and social problem requiring a comprehensive approach to diagnosis, prevention and treatment. Adolescence is accompanied by intensive physical, hormonal and psychoemotional development, which makes the cardiovascular system particularly vulnerable. Against the background of stress, anxiety, increased psycho-emotional stress and unhealthy lifestyle can occur functional disorders of the heart, which, in the absence of timely measures, can be transformed into persistent diseases.

Modern diagnostic methods, such as ECG, echocardiography, Holter monitoring and psychological testing, allow timely detection of hidden disorders, assessing not only physiological but also psycho-emotional aspects of adolescent health. At the same time, effective prevention includes the formation of a healthy lifestyle, reducing stress levels, creating a favourable psychological environment and regular medical monitoring. Special attention should be paid to early identification of risk factors and their elimination, which is possible only with the active role of the family, educational institutions and the health care system.

Thus, the prevention of cardiosomatic disorders in adolescents is possible through a multidisciplinary approach that includes medical, educational and social-psychological measures. Involvement of adolescents in the process of forming a healthy lifestyle, development of stress resistance skills and creation of a supportive environment will minimise the risks of cardiosomatic disorders and ensure harmonious development during this important period of life.

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